

EVALUATION OF THE RESISTANCE OF POTATO MICROTUBERS TO ABIOTIC AND BIOTIC STRESSES IN THE ENVIRONMENT USING A BIOSTIMULANT

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Аннотация. Картошка (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) — дунё миқёсидаги муҳим озуқа экинларидан бири бўлиб, уни *in vitro* шароитида кўпайтириши ва микротуганаклар етиштириши орқали самарадорлигини ошириши мумкин. Тадқиқотда Мурасиге – Скуг озиқа мухитига ДАГ-1 биостимуляторининг турли концентрациялари (10^{-5} – 10^{-8} М) кўшилиб картошканинг Red Scarlet нави ўсимлигига таъсири ўрганилди. Бунда 10^{-8} М концентрация ўсимлик ривожланишига энг самарали таъсир кўрсатди. 10^{-6} М концентрация эса микротуганаклар сонини кўпайтирди ва физиологик кўрсаткичларни яхшилади. Пероксидаза фаоллигининг ортиши билан водород пероксид миқдорининг камайиши, биостимулятор таркибидаги салицил кислотаси орқали антиоксидант тизим фаоллашганидан далолат беради. Ушбу натижалар ДАГ-1 препарати картошканинг *in vitro* кўпайтирилиши ва микротуганак етиштириши жараёнларида самарали биостимулятор сифатида фойдаланилиши мумкинлигини кўрсатди.

Калим сўзлар: *Solanum tuberosum* L., *in vitro*, биостимулятор, микротуганак, бўгин оралиги, пероксидаза, водород пероксид.

Аннотация. Картофель (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) является одной из важнейших продовольственных культур в мире, и его продуктивность может быть повышена за счёт размножения в условиях *in vitro* и получения микроклубней. В исследовании изучалось влияние различных концентраций биостимулятора ДАГ-1 (10^{-5} – 10^{-8} М), добавленного в питательную среду Мурасиге-Скуга, на растения картофеля сорта Red Scarlet. Наиболее эффективное влияние на развитие растений оказала концентрация 10^{-8} М. Концентрация 10^{-6} М способствовала увеличению количества микроклубней и улучшению физиологических показателей. Повышение активности пероксидазы при одновременном снижении уровня перекиси водорода свидетельствует об активации антиоксидантной системы за счёт салициловой кислоты, входящей в состав биостимулятора. Полученные результаты показывают, что препарат ДАГ-1 может эффективно использоваться в качестве биостимулятора при *in vitro* размножении картофеля и получении микроклубней.

Ключевые слова: *Solanum tuberosum* L., *in vitro*, биостимулятор, микроклубень, междоузлия, пероксидаза, водород пероксид.

Abstract. Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is one of the most important food crops worldwide, and its productivity can be enhanced through *in vitro* propagation and microtuber production. In this study, the effect of various concentrations (10^{-5} – 10^{-8} M) of the

biostimulator DAG-1 added to Murashige and Skoog (MS) nutrient medium on the potato cultivar Red Scarlet was investigated. The concentration of 10^{-8} M had the most effective impact on plant development. A concentration of 10^{-6} M increased the number of microtubers and improved physiological parameters. An increase in peroxidase activity accompanied by a decrease in hydrogen peroxide content indicates activation of the antioxidant system due to the salicylic acid present in the biostimulator. These results demonstrate that DAG-1 can be effectively used as a biostimulant in the processes of in vitro propagation and microtuber production in potato.

Keywords: *Solanum tuberosum L., in vitro, biostimulator, microtuber, internode, peroxidase, hydrogen peroxide.*

The potato plant (*Solanum tuberosum L.*) is an annual vegetable crop and ranks fourth among agricultural crops worldwide. One of the drawbacks of propagating this plant is the susceptibility of seed tubers to biotic and abiotic stresses, which complicates the process of obtaining healthy planting material. In recent years, a system for controlling and accelerating morphogenetic processes under in vitro conditions through microtuber production has been developed. Growth regulators are commonly used in in vitro propagation, germination, and microtuber production [1]. Currently, exogenous growth regulators are being used to stimulate tuber formation under in vitro conditions [2,3]. Treating most plants with growth regulators (phytohormones, salicylic acid, biologically active compounds) positively affects their productivity [4].

According to the literature, salicylic acid affects a number of physiological processes in plants [5]. In particular, the DAG-1 biostimulant (a supramolecular complex of glycyrrhizin and salicylic acid) was developed at the Bioorganic Chemistry Institute of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, named after A.S. Sadiqov [6]. This study was conducted to investigate the effect of various concentrations of the biostimulant (10^{-5} M - 10^{-8} M) added to the Murashige-Skoog nutrient medium on improving plant cultivation methods and influencing the tuber formation process. In vitro, on the 28th day of the Red Scarlet variety, stem length, internode length, and root number were observed, and on the 60th day of the vegetation period, the number of microtubers was recorded, and results were obtained. The results of the conducted research showed that the 10^{-8} M concentration had a significant positive effect on the rate of plant development. In the studied potato variety, the stem length was found to be 1.21 times higher compared to the control. The number of internodes is an important morphological characteristic that enhances the regeneration ability of genotypes and, accordingly, increases the multiplication rate of microplants. Therefore, the number of internodes remained unchanged compared to the control.

The 10^{-6} M concentration of the biostimulant had a positive effect on the plant: stem length decreased by 5.5 cm compared to the control, while the number of internodes increased by 7.4 times. The number of roots was 6.5 cm in the control and 3.5 cm in the treated sample, and the number of microtubers was 15 cm in the control and 22.2 cm in the sample.

Changes in the growth and development of plants cultivated under in vitro conditions were found to depend on the concentration of additives in the nutrient medium and the plant variety. At concentrations of 10^{-6} M and 10^{-8} M, the biostimulant caused differences in plant length and internode spacing compared to the control, and the number of microtubers was higher than in the control, indicating improved results.

During our study, biochemical indicators showed that peroxidase enzyme activity at the 10^{-6} M concentration of the biostimulant was 1.73 times higher than in the control, which, in turn, led to a 1.31-fold decrease in hydrogen peroxide content compared to the control (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Peroxidase enzyme activity and hydrogen peroxide content in microclones of the Red Scarlet potato cultivar grown in nutrient media with different concentrations of the DAG-1 preparation.

The salicylic acid in the composition of the DAG-1 preparation activates the peroxidase enzyme, leading to a reduction of H_2O_2 in the cell. In this process, salicylic acid, which stimulates glutathione metabolism, acts as a secondary messenger in the signaling pathway for the activation of defense-related genes. Glutathione participates in the detoxification of H_2O_2 and protects the cell from various oxidative stresses by maintaining the thiol state of cytoplasmic membrane components. The decrease in H_2O_2 levels is likely the result of the functional activity of the antioxidant system, which corresponds well with a low level of lipid peroxidation.

Materials and Methods

The MS medium was supplemented with separate concentrations of the DAG-1 stimulator — 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} , 10^{-7} , and 10^{-8} M. Internodes of microclones were used as explants, which were cultivated under light conditions of 1500–2000 lux, a temperature of 20–22°C, and a photoperiod of 16/8 (day/night). For each variant, 40 explants were used with three replicates. The results were analyzed using the "Origin 8" software.

The microplants were homogenized in the presence of liquid nitrogen. The protein extract was obtained using a 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 6.6, containing 0.5 M NaCl (1:3), for 1 hour at 4°C. The samples were centrifuged for 20 minutes at 5000 rpm. Peroxidase activity was determined using the Boyarkin method [7]. Protein content was determined using the Lowry method [8]. The hydrogen peroxide content was determined using the Alexieva method [9]. The data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using OriginPro 7.0 software.

Conclusion

The research results confirmed a significant correlation between two important physiological processes — morphological and biochemical responses in plants. Moreover, the manifestation of these processes is a specific characteristic of the cultivated variety and may contribute to increasing the productivity of potato plants in the future.

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